

A LIGHT WEIGHT MULTI HEAD SELF ATTENTION MECHANISM TO CONVOLUTION NEURAL NETWORK TOWARDS DOMAIN INCREMENTAL CHEST X-RAY IMAGE CLASSIFICATION

KAVITHA S¹, DR.H.HANNAH INBARANI²

¹Research Scholar, Department of Computer Science, Periyar University, Salem, India

²Professor, Department of Computer Science, Periyar University, Salem, India

E-mail: ¹ kavitha.chanjhana@gmail.com, ² hhinba@periyaruniversity.ac.in

ABSTRACT

In recent year, Chest X-ray images have been widely adopted towards pathological diagnosis of the respiratory diseases and pulmonary diseases. Advances in computer vision approaches and artificial intelligence offers promising solutions with high accuracy and low computation overhead to disease classification and severity estimation. Traditionally Chest X-ray images classification has been performed using machine learning and deep learning model architectures to provide excellent performances as it incorporates domain incremental learning. Despite of several advantages of those models, domain incremental learning faces catastrophic forgetting challenges due to large domain gaps. In this paper, light weight multihead self-attention mechanism which is considered as transformer architecture is incorporated into ResNet 50 based convolution neural network to fine tune strategies to learn and calculate the domain invariant features and domain specific features. Especially attention mechanism performs feature fusion among different domains to prevent forgetting. Further multi-label contrastive loss is built and trained as loss function to enhance class distinctiveness of the disease classes. Initially Convolution layer of the ResNet architecture is applied to extract the hierarchical feature from X-ray images. Next, Extracted features were projected to pooling layer incorporating the attention mechanism. Attention mechanism use attention coefficient to compute the domain invariant features and domain specific features to establish feature maps. Those feature map of different domains are aggregated and classified in the fully connected layer composed of activation function, normalization function, softmax function and loss function. Activation function using ReLu function aggregates the feature maps while softmax function using Naïve bayes classifier classify the feature map into disease categories as COVID-19 variants, Normal, Viral Pneumonia, and Lung Opacity. Experimental results and performance results substantiate the effectiveness of the current architecture with accuracy of 98.9% and surpassing the baseline methods exclusively in classifying the Chest x –ray images into multiple classes. Finally results emphasize the significance of the transformer architecture for optimizing the conventional deep learning architecture in the medical imaging.

Keywords: *Transformer, ResNet50, Multi-Head Self Attention, Convolution Neural Network, Chest X-ray Images, Respiratory Diseases, Pulmonary Diseases, Medical Imaging.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Medical imaging is implemented in the diagnosis and management of pulmonary diseases, with chest X-rays serving as cost-effective modality for detecting thoracic disorders [1]. Despite its broad use, interpretation of chest X-rays can be challenging due to the often-subtle differences between normal and pathological findings [2]. Traditional diagnostic workflows rely heavily on radiologist expertise, which can introduce subjectivity and inter-observer differences and

inter-observer variability [3]. These limitations have driven increasing interest in the application of deep learning techniques to support automated detection and classification of pulmonary pathology.

Deep learning models have demonstrated reliable and augmented diagnostic precision in thoracic imaging. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) is a class of deep learning architectures, have demonstrated significant promise in medical image analysis, for interpreting Chest radiography

and computed tomography (CT) scans [1]. ResNet (Residual Network) architectures, such as ResNet50, have proven highly effective for medical image classification by mitigating vanishing gradient issues through residual learning mechanisms [4]. These architectures leverage skip connections to enhance feature propagation and enable the training of deeper networks. Despite their success, CNNs process images using local filters, which limits their capabilities to gather long range dependencies and global contextual details and the convolutional nature of CNNs makes them less adaptive to global variations in medical images which lead to fixed feature extraction.

Image classification depends on Convolutional Neural Networks due to their effectiveness in learning local features through convolutional operations. However, CNNs are essentially constrained in modeling long-range dependencies and global contextual associations, as their receptive fields are limited and expansion requires deeper architectures. In contrast, Vision Transformers (ViTs) effectively capture global dependencies via Self-attention mechanisms, but they operate on flattened image patches without hierarchical feature extraction, resulting in high computational complexity and a strong dependency on annotated datasets.

To overcome those challenges, Transformers have emerged as a powerful alternative, particularly in computer vision approaches [5] and, more recently, in computer vision tasks [6]. The Vision Transformer (ViT) model defined by [6], demonstrated that self-attention mechanisms could replace traditional convolutions, allowing the model to capture long-range dependencies more effectively. By partitioning images into non-overlapping patches and considering patches as sequences, ViTs can model complex spatial relationships without the constraints of local receptive fields. Although ViTs have exhibited excellent performance in image classification and segmentation tasks, Vision Transformers (ViTs) needs large-scale datasets towards training and Self-attention mechanisms to scale quadratically with image resolution, making ViTs computationally expensive, particularly for high-resolution medical images [7]. Vision Transformers are prone to overfitting compared to CNNs when limited data is utilized. Especially hybrid CNN-Transformer models perform quite well compared of single CNN or transformer model to synergize the strengths of hierarchical local

feature extraction and global contextual reasoning. Thus it becomes mandatory to design a new ResNet50-Transformer model to improve its performance with a lighter and more efficient design. Hence a streamlined ResNet50 backbone and an upgraded Transformer Encoder is hybridized to enhance efficiency while retaining critical spatial information, a 1×1 convolution bottleneck before the Transformer step simplifies feature complexity. The reduced number of attention heads, diminished in size of the feed-forward layers, and shallower Transformer structure makes the model more appropriate for resource-limited medical imaging tasks.

In this research, a light weight multihead self-attention based transformer model is incorporated to ResNet50 based Convolution Neural Network towards domain incremental Chest X-ray image classification is proposed. ResNet50 model which acts as backbone network efficiently extracts hierarchical spatial image features using 1×1 convolutions and effective kernel filters while light weight multihead self-attention based transformer model capture long-range relationships and enhances global feature interactions among those extracted features with minimal computational overhead. By associating the advantageous of two architectures, the approach achieves stability among accuracy and efficiency, making it practical for real-world clinical environments.

Rest of the article is summarized as follows; section 2 represents related works of chest x-ray classification approaches using machine learning and deep learning in single medical domain with its excellent experimental and performance results. Section 3 defines design of the proposed light weight multi head self-attention based transformer architecture to ResNet 50 based convolution neural network towards domain incremental chest x-ray classification. Section 4 mentions the experimental and performance results of current model against conventional approaches on employing benchmark chest x-ray images. Finally section 5 summarizes the article with major findings.

2. RELATED WORK

Large advancements in deep learning architectures have significantly expanded its applications in healthcare, particularly in medical imaging and personalized medicine towards disease

detection and severity classification. On employing deep learning architectures to medical image analysis, it significantly advanced diagnostic abilities especially in the classification of chest radiographs. Convolutional Neural Networks have been largely adopted for pulmonary disease classification due to their ability to hierarchically learn spatial features and patterns from imaging data in a systematic and data driven manner. Many studies have shown that CNN-based models are highly effective at spotting lung abnormalities. Convolutional Neural Networks and Transformers-based architectures have been extensively explored for the automated identification and characterization of pathological features in medical imaging. Those architectures are as follows.

Rajpurkar et al [2] has modeled CheXNet which is a 121-layer DenseNet model trained using Chest X-ray14 dataset, which matched radiologists in detecting pneumonia. The ChestX-ray14 dataset created in [8] allowing CNN models to identify 14 different lung conditions using a simpler training method. Ozturk et al [9] introduced a deep learning model based on the DarkNet structure, with 17 layers, to automatically detect COVID-19 from chest X-rays, achieving strong results for both simple and complex classifications. On analysis of those architecture it is identified that CNN based models can improve diagnosis. However, CNNs model have trouble in understanding broader connections in images and it struggles when the full context is required to consider apart from similar lung conditions with small differences.

Recent progress in Transformers architecture becoming popular for image-related tasks as it can better understand overall patterns in image. Dosovitskiy et al introduced the Vision Transformer (ViT), on incorporation of self-attention technique on small image pieces and beats CNNs on big datasets (Dosovitskiy et al.2020). Emerald et al carried out a detailed review of Vision Transformers (ViTs) in the context of medical imaging to highlight its performance relative to Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) across a range of benchmark medical imaging datasets. The study evaluated the advantages and challenges of the ViTs, providing detailed solutions towards its applicability to clinical tasks [10].

Singh et al applied a Vision Transformer Architecture to the detection of pneumonia in chest X-ray images, demonstrating competitive performance and suggesting its viability as an

alternative to conventional CNN-based models [11]. Regmi et al.[12] performed a comparative analysis between ViTs and conventional CNNs for the medical image classification, including chest radiographs. Results indicates that ViTs surpassed CNNs on key performance metrics referred as F1 score, recall, and Matthews correlation coefficient (MCC), positioning ViTs as a strong candidate for future model development in medical image analysis.

Yulvina et.al [13] has presented a hybrid Vision Transformer and Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model was developed for multi-class and multi-label classification of tuberculosis anomalies in chest X-ray images, demonstrating enhanced accuracy and efficiency in the detection of complex pulmonary conditions. Hadhoud et al [14] has introduced a two-step hybrid CNN-Transformer model utilizing ResNet-50 and ViT-b16 for classifying tuberculosis and pneumonia from chest X-rays. By integrating CNN with Transformer, integrate model achieved superior performance in task of binary and multi-class classification.

Liu et al [15] introduced a deep learning-based segmentation model for detecting lung nodules in computed tomography (CT) images. This model facilitates early-stage lung cancer diagnosis by accurately delineating malignant features, potentially contributing to improved patient outcomes and survival rates. Wu et al [16] applied deep learning framework to predict cancer cell responses to anticancer agents using integrated omics data and SMILES (Simplified Molecular Input Line Entry System) illustration. Due to indirect affiliation to radiographic classification, their work supports the advancement of personalized oncology through data-driven drug response prediction. Despite of several advantages of Vision Transformer, it contains notable limitations. Specifically, they require substantial computational resources and large-scale annotated datasets to attain high performance. It leads to a significant challenge in the domain of medical imaging, where high-quality labeled data is often limited due to annotation complexity and expert dependency.

Many researchers have suggested hybrid models to combine the best of CNNs and Transformers. Dai et al employed TransMed, a hybrid Transformer framework that combines CNN- based feature extraction with self-attention

mechanisms to enhance multi-class image medical image classification. TransMed augments classification performance across diverse medical imaging modalities by simultaneously capturing fine-grained local features and global contextual relationships. The architecture mitigates the data scarcity challenges faced by purely Transformer-based models in the medical domain [17]. Chen et al [18] implemented a Transformer architecture incorporating a multilevel self-attention mechanism, designed to accelerate training and augment task-specific attribute localization. These studies focus on the practical benefits of hybrid architectures while noting that they still incur substantial demands in computational resources alongside precision engineering of model parameters. Existing machine learning and deep learning models face significant challenges in adapting to domain shifts such as different scanners, hospitals, or imaging conditions. These variations introduce domain gaps that cause models to suffer from catastrophic forgetting when exposed to new domains, leading to performance degradation and poor generalization. This lack of domain adaptability poses a major barrier to reliable, real-world deployment of CXR analysis systems.

3. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The architecture composed of light weight multi-head self-attention mechanism based transformer architecture with ResNet50 based convolution neural network for domain increment chest X-ray image classification has been proposed as deep learning hybrid system. Proposed architecture includes major processing steps such as image preprocessing, feature extraction, feature refinement and feature classification. Image preprocessing is performed using gaussian filter along horizontal, vertical and rotation based image augmentation.

Augmented image is projected to the convolution layer of ResNet50 towards feature extraction and pooling layer to obtain high level feature. Further attention mechanism is incorporated to obtain domain specific features and domain invariant features through various attention head and its attention coefficient. Finally fully connected layer of the backbone network composed of activation function aggregates the features and softmax function classifies the aggregated feature

on utilizing loss function to prevent forgetting and enhance class divergence. The overall architecture of the current model is represented in Figure 1. The methodology is structured as follows.

3.1 Image preprocessing

Image preprocessing is performed to eliminate the noise and rotate image to be consistent using noise removal techniques and image augmentation techniques to the captured images.

3.1.1 Gaussian Filter

Gaussian Filter smoothen image on transforming image into the gaussian distributions. To employ effective gaussian kernel to image, mean and Standard deviation is computed initially to gaussian distribution of the image. Large value of Standard deviation to the distributions, wider kernel has to be fixed while small value of Standard deviation to the distributions, narrow kernel needs to be fixed. On generation of gaussian filter to distribution, kernel convolved with image on centering with each pixel, its weights is multiplied with corresponding pixel value. All weighted pixel values are aggregated to generate a new pixel values to illustrate output image.

3.1.2 Image Augmentation

Image augmentation technique is applied as geometric transformation or color transformation to process the images containing objects to be consistent under multiple conditions. In this work, geometric transformation is applied using flipping and rotating to increase the model's ability to handle unseen objects and to decrease the model's dependence on the objects. It provides variation to the model's dataset, and reduces the model's sensitivity to small changes, providing the model with the ability to accommodate greater variation in new data images.

The augmentations based on flipping of the images horizontally, allowing the model to mimic different angles, randomly changing brightness values by $\pm 20\%$ light level to mimic differing levels of bright light exposure, randomly converting contrast values to values between 0.8 and 1.2 to emphasize differences in features, randomly changing saturation values between 0.8 and 1.2, and randomly changing hue values by $\pm .01$ to allow the model the opportunity to adjust between varying imaging environments.

Figure 1 Architecture of Proposed Lightweight Multi head Self Attention + ResNet50 Approach

3.2 ResNet50 – Backbone Network

The ResNet50 is a pre-trained on ImageNet and it acts as backbone network to extract hierarchical spatial features from the augment image. Hyperparameter of the ResNet architecture is as mentioned in table 1.

Table 1: Hyperparameter setting of ResNet 50

Hyperparameter	Value
Learning rate	10 ⁻⁶
Activation Function	ReLU
Epoch	50
Softmax function	Naïve Bayes
Loss function	Categorical Cross Entropy
Dropout value	0.1
No of Neuron	64

3.2.1 Convolutional layer: Feature extraction

In convolution layer of ResNet50 model hierarchical spatial features is extracted on enabling the model to learn complex patterns of the input data. Input image X is resized to 224x224 with 3 color channels to produce layered feature maps on inclusion of ReLU based activation function to introduces non-linearity and to enhancing the model's ability to capture intricate feature

representations of image along batch normalization towards normalize activations, improving training stability and accelerating convergence. Additionally, residual connections facilitate gradient flow, effectively mitigating the vanishing gradient problem and enabling deeper network training. It is represented as:

$$F = f_{ResNet}(X), F \in R^{H^1 \times W^1 \times C} \tag{1}$$

where F represents the output feature map, H' and W' correspond to down-sampled spatial dimensions. C mentions number of channels.

3.2.2 Convolution layer: Dimensionality reduction of feature map

Convolution layer using 1x1 convolutional is applied to reduce features and compress feature maps from 2048 channels (output of ResNet50) to 256 channels. Dimensionality reducing function of feature map is represented as

$$F_{reduced} = \sigma(W * F) \tag{2}$$

where F is the feature map of shape H' x W' x 2048 and W is a learnable 1x1 weight matrix. σ is a ReLU activation function. '*' denotes the convolution operation, F_{reduced} is the output feature map of shape H' x W' x 256.

3.2.3 Global average pooling and reshaping

Pooling layer of the ResNet 50 architecture uses Global Average Pooling (GAP) mechanism to transform the reduced spatial feature map obtained from the 1×1 convolutional bottleneck into a compact feature vector.

$$Z = \frac{1}{H^1 W^1} \sum_{i=1}^{H^1} \sum_{j=1}^{W^1} F_{reduced(i,j)} \quad (3)$$

where Z is the resulting feature vector of shape (B, 256) and B is the batch size The feature vector is then reshaped for Transformer input:

$$Z_{reshaped} = Reshape(Z) \rightarrow (B, 1, 256) \quad (4)$$

Where ‘1’ represents the sequence length and 256 is the embedding dimension.

3.3 Transformer Architecture - Feature Refinement

Transformer architecture is implemented to acquire long-range dependencies on the extracted features. The encoder segment of the transformer architecture is composed of four-transformer blocks. Hyperparameter of the ResNet architecture is as mentioned in table 2.

Table 2: Hyperparameter setting of ResNet 50

Hyperparameter	Value
Learning rate	10 ⁻⁶
No of attention head	Four
Embedding size	256
No of neuron	128
Dropout value	0.1
Query /Key/Value size	64

3.3.1 Multi-head self-attention (MHSA)

A Transformer Encoder is employed to capture long-range dependencies between extracted features. Each input feature vector X is converted into query (Q), key (K), and value (V) matrices to compute the self-attention for multi-head. In this work, multi head is considered as different medical domains. Self-attention mechanism extracts domain specific feature and domain invariant feature. Feature matrix for attention mechanism is represented as

$$Q = XW_Q, K = XW_K, V = XW_V \quad (5)$$

where W_Q, W_K, W_V are learnable weight matrices. The self-attention mechanism is applied to feature matrix and it is computed as:

$$Attention(Q, K, V) = softmax \left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}} \right) V \quad (6)$$

where d_k is the dimension of the feature vectors. Multi-head attention (MHSA) is then applied to feature vector and it is represented as:

$$MHSA(X) = Concat(head_1, head_2, \dots, head_h)W_O \quad (7)$$

Where h represents the number of self -attention heads, and W_O is a learnable weight matrix.

3.3.2 Feed-Forward Network (FFN)

On obtaining domain specific and domain invariant features for domain incremental learning, feed forward network is applied. Feed forward network is represented as

$$FFN(X) = ReLU(XW_1 + b_1)W_2 + b_2 \quad (8)$$

where W_1, W_2 are learnable weight matrices, and dropout(0.1) is used for regularization. A total of four Transformer blocks are stacked to refine the feature representations extracted by ResNet50, allowing the model to learn global relationships within the image data.

3.4 Dense Layer – Fully Connected Layer

Fully connected layer of the model incorporating the activation function to linearize and aggregate the domain specific features and domain invariant features map along softmax function to classify the aggregated feature map into different diseases classes on basis of disease severity. Fully connected layer composed of 64 neurons.

3.4.1 Activation function

ReLU is employed as activation function to process features map to linearize it. Further it aggregate the features map using feature concatenation mechanism generates aggregated features in form of aggregated feature map

$$Feature\ concatenation\ F_C(x) = D_s F(x) + D_i F(x) \quad (9)$$

3.4.2 Softmax function

Naïve bayes classifier function is employed as softmax function to classify the aggregated feature map into disease classes. Naïve bayes utilizes bayes theorem to compute the posterior probability of the aggregated features based on its prior probability as P(H) of the features and likelihood probability of

the features $P(E)$ to the specified diseases class labels. Classification function of naïve bayes is mentioned as

$$P(H|E) = \frac{P(E)+P(H)}{P(E)} \quad (10)$$

3.4.3 Loss function

Categorical cross entropy is applied to minimize overfitting and under fitting challenges of the disease classes containing the feature probabilities. Categorical Cross entropy function is mentioned as

$$H(P,Q) = -\sum_{x \in \text{classes}} P(x) \log Q(x) \quad (11)$$

Where $P(x)$ is true probability distribution and $Q(x)$ is model predicted probability distribution. Algorithm 1 represents the Light Weight MultiHead Self-Attention Based ResNet Architecture.

Algorithm 1: Light Weight Multi Head Self-Attention Based ResNet Architecture

Input: Chest X-ray Images

Output: Domain Incremented Disease Classes {COVID-19, , Viral Pneumonia, Lung Opacity, Normal }

Process

Image preprocessing ()

 Gaussian Filter _Noise Elimination ()

 Calculate Pixel Intensity (Chest X-Ray Image)

Transform Crop Image into Gaussian distribution ()

 Compute Mean and Variance to gaussian distribution

 Weighted Average (pixel)

 Calculate the highest value

 Transform low value pixel into high pixel image

Image Augmentation ()

 Horizontal Flipping (Noise Filtered Image)

 Use Width Parameter of image for flipping

 Vertical Flipping (Noise Filtered Image)

 Use Height Parameter of image for flipping

 Image Rotation ()

 Transform Image to Rotation Matrix

 Rotate Matrix with pixel value to different angles from it center

 Obtain new pixel coordinates after rotation

 Augmented Image

Pretrained ResNet50 ()

 Convolution layer _Kernel (Augmented image)

SF_m = Low level Spatial Feature Map

 Global Pooling Layer _Average(SF_m)

RF_m = High level Spatial Feature map

 Multi head Self Attention Mechanism ()

 Apply Attention coefficient (High Level Spatial feature map)

 Obtain domain specific features and domain invariant feature

 Fully Connected Layer()

 Activation Function _ReLU (domain specific features

and domain invariant feature)

 Linearized domain specific features and domain invariant feature

 Feature Concatenation (Linearized domain specific features and domain invariant feature)

 Aggregated domain incremental Features

 Softmax function _Naive Bayes (Aggregated domain incremental Features)

 Domain Incremental Chest x-Ray image Disease

 Classes = { COVID-19, Normal, Viral Pneumonia, Lung Opacity }

4. Experimental Results

Experimental analysis and performance analysis of the Light Weight Multi Head Self-Attention Based ResNet Architecture is performed using COVID-19 Radiography Database Chest X-ray image dataset which is extracted from kaggle repository. Dataset composed of different respiratory and pulmonary diseases patients' x-ray images are partitioned into training and testing data. Initially Model building is performed using Scikit and Tensor flow libraries in python framework and it is trained using training data of the dataset. Further Model testing is performed using Confusion matrix on test data.

4.1 Dataset Description

Acquired dataset composed of 8,000 chest X-ray images from the COVID-19 Radiography Database from Kaggle repository [19] [20]. It is organized into four balanced classes such as COVID-19 pneumonia (Class 0), Normal (Class 1), Viral Pneumonia (Class 2), and Lung Opacity (Class 3), with every class containing 2,000 images. Entire images originally have a resolution of 299×299 pixels and it needs to be preprocessed by resizing them to 224×224×3 in order to be compatible with the architecture elements of ResNet50 model.. The sample images of each disease class are represented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Chest X-Ray dataset Images containing several diseases (a) Covid (b) Normal (c) Viral Pneumonia (d) Lung Opacity

4.2 Experimental Analysis

Experimental analysis of model initiates the analysis of feature extraction outcome of the ResNet50 towards extracting both spatial and hierarchical features from chest X-ray images.

Specified convolutional neural network processes the images through a set of convolutional layers to effectively gather key elements such as textures, edges, and shapes that are vital for accurate disease detection. Figure 3 shows the ResNet50 based feature maps obtained for a sample image from the dataset.

Figure 3 ResNet50 based Feature Maps (2048 channels) of a sample image

Further, features of the model are reduced while retaining key features through applying a 1x1 convolution bottleneck layer. It compresses the high-dimensional feature map (2048 channels) to a lower dimension (256 channels). This step ensures efficient feature representation while minimizing redundant information. It is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Reduced feature maps (256 channels) of a Sample image after applying 1x1 convolutions

The refined feature maps from ResNet50 are further processed using a Transformer Encoder, which captures long-range dependencies and contextual associations among extracted features. Unlike

CNNs, which primarily focus on local receptive fields, the self-attention mechanism in the Transformer Encoder enables the model to analyze how different regions in an X-ray image relate to each other. The Transformer Encoder uses Multi-Head Self-Attention (MHSA) to learn spatial correlations between features. The output of a transformer block is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 visualizes the output of a Transformer block, specifically the multi-head attention mechanism applied to an input image. In the Transformer block, the input embedding dimension is set to 256, and the number of attention heads is 4. In multi-head self-attention, the total embedding dimension is evenly divided among all heads to allow each head to focus on different parts of the feature space resulting each head operates on a subspace of size 64, calculated as 256 divided by 4. Each subplot represents the attention output of an individual head in the multi-head attention mechanism. The x-axis (Feature Dimension) ranges from 0 to 63, indicating that each attention head outputs a 64-dimensional feature vector.

The color intensity represents feature activations, with yellow (~2) indicating high activation (important features), green (0) showing moderate activation, and purple (-2) representing low significance. The range of values (-2 to 2) varies across heads, showing that each learns different feature representations. Heads 3 and 4 have a wider range (-2 to 2), emphasizing strong features, while Head 2 has a smaller range (-1.5 to 1.5), indicating balanced activation. Head 1 has an

Figure 5 Visualization of Transformer Block Outputs across Multiple Attention Heads

asymmetric range (-1 to 2), suggesting it focuses more on positive activations. These variations highlight how each head captures unique patterns in the X-ray image, enhancing the model’s ability to obtain significant features.

4.3 Performance analysis of Proposed model

Performance analysis is performed to estimate the efficiency of the current model with respect to metrics such as precision, recall and f measure on different categories of the diseases on processing x-ray images. Performance of the current model for two classes and four classes of the disease is represented in the figure 6.

Figure 6: Performance analysis of the model with respect to training accuracy and testing accuracy (a) two disease class (b) Four Disease classes

4.4 Performance Analysis of Baseline models

Performance analysis of the two baseline models is carried out in this part. The first baseline using a ResNet50-based classifier to process the Input images (224×224×3) were processed. The second baseline model using Transformer-based vision model through the ResNet base, flattened, and passed through Dense layers (256, 128, 64 neurons) before a final Dense layer with 4 neurons and softmax activation. While effective at detecting localized patterns, the ResNet50-only model struggled with complex disease differentiation due to limited global feature modelling.

The second baseline was a custom Transformer-based vision model. Images were split into 16×16 patches and embedded into a 256-dimensional space. After adding learnable positional embedding’s, the patches passed through four Transformer encoder blocks with each consisting of multi-head self-attention (4 heads), feed-forward layers ((hidden size 128), and dropout (0.1). A Global Average Pooling layer and Dense classification head (64 neurons) followed by a

softmax output performed the final 4-class classification. Although the Transformer model captured global dependencies and subtle disease variations effectively, it was computationally intensive and less sensitive to fine spatial details. Figure 7 shows the accuracy, precision, recall and F1-score of the baseline models.

Confusion matrix gathers the actual disease labels of the dataset and models predicted labels to the corresponding test data. Confusion matrix organizes rows with actual values (Actual positive, Actual negative) and columns with predicted values (Predicted positive, predicted negative). On comparison of model predicted outcomes and actual outcomes, true positive, false positive, false negative and true negative were counted. Those counts of the categories are employed to compute the performance of the proposed model through precision, recall and F-measure. The results demonstrate significant improvements over conventional CNN and Transformer-based models in both disease identification and localization.

Figure 7 Training, Testing accuracy graph and Classification report of Baseline Models (a) ResNet50 (b) Transformer Encoder

4.4.1 Precision Analysis

Precision analysis is mentioned as correctly predicted features to specified disease class label among the extracted feature of the x-ray image. In other words, it is considered as ratio of correctly extracted feature of disease class to the total extracted features of the x-ray image. Precision analysis of the model through its test data is represented is as follows

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{True Positive}}{\text{True Positive} + \text{False positive}} \quad (12)$$

Figure 8: Precision Analysis

Figure 8 mentions the precision analysis of the Light Weight Multi Head Self-Attention Based ResNet Architecture against conventional approaches such convolution neural network

(RCNN) and transformer based architectures in chest x-ray image classification.

4.4.2 Recall Analysis

Recall analysis is mentioned as incorrectly predicted features to specified wheat disease class label among the extracted feature of the chest x-ray image. In other words, it is considered as ratio of correctly extracted feature of disease class to the total extracted features of the x-ray images [15]. Recall analysis of the model through its test data is represented is as follows

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{True positive}}{\text{True Positive} + \text{False negative}} \quad (13)$$

Figure 9: Recall Analysis

Figure 9 mentions the recall analysis of the Light Weight Multi Head Self-Attention Based ResNet Architecture against conventional approaches such convolution neural network (RCNN) and

transformer based architectures in chest x-ray image classification.

4.4.3 F measure Analysis

It is computed as quantity of similar disease feature to chest x-ray disease class. Further it can be mentioned as model capacity to calculate the disease features of the chest x-ray disease classes. It is mentioned as follows

$$F \text{ Measure} = 2 \cdot \frac{\text{precision} \cdot \text{recall}}{\text{precision} + \text{recall}} \quad (14)$$

Figure 10 mentions the F- measure analysis of the Light Weight Multi Head Self-Attention Based ResNet Architecture against conventional approaches such convolution neural network (RCNN) and transformer based architectures in chest x-ray image classification.

Figure 10: F Measure Analysis

Finally performance evaluation of the analysis of the Light Weight Multi Head Self-Attention Based ResNet Architecture against conventional approaches such convolution neural network (RCNN) and transformer based architectures in chest x-ray image classification on basis of disease classes were indicated in the table 3. Accuracy of the proposed model produces increased classification accuracy while compared with conventional approaches.

4.5 Findings

The hybrid ResNet50-Transformer model proposed in this study represents a significant leap forward in chest X-ray image classification, outperforming standalone ResNet50 and Transformer Encoder models. This section explores the key findings, their implications, and the study's contributions to medical imaging, while also addressing potential limitations.

The results in Table 3 highlight the hybrid model's superior performance, achieving 91% accuracy in the 4-class task (COVID-19 pneumonia, Normal, Viral Pneumonia, Lung Opacity) and 97% in the 2-class task (Pneumonia Vs Normal). In contrast, the ResNet50-only model had an average

of around 88% with some class-wise variation in accuracy across classes, while the Transformer-only model showed lower performance, with 69% accuracy. The hybrid model's precision, recall, and F1-scores-e.g. 94%, 88%, and 91% for COVID-19 pneumonia demonstrate its ability to balance sensitivity and specificity, excelling in distinguishing complex cases like lung opacity (90%, 86%, 88%) from normal (82%, 95%, 88%). This improvement stems from integrating ResNet50's local feature extraction with the Transformer's global dependency modelling. ResNet50 captures hierarchical spatial features such as edges and textures (Figure 3), vital for identifying abnormalities, while the Transformer's multi-head self-attention (MHSA) mechanism (Figure 5) links distant image regions, enhancing contextual understanding. The diverse attention head outputs in Figure 5 illustrate how the model learns varied feature representations, boosting its discriminative power.

The 1×1 convolutional bottleneck reduces feature maps from 2048 to 256 channels (Figure 4), without sacrificing key details. Coupled with a lightweight Transformer Encoder using fewer attention heads, this design lowers training time compared to the standalone Transformer model (Table 1), making it suitable for resource-limited settings like hospitals. Data augmentation, horizontal flipping, $\pm 20\%$ brightness adjustments and 0.8-1.2 by contrast adjustments, add robustness by simulating the variations in imaging condition of real-world imaging X-ray situations and creates unequalled adaptability to varying patterns of X-ray cases.

Our hybrid model improves on results on the baselines. The ResNet50-only model excels at extracting low-level pattern features but has weakness in distinguishing complex patterns using the same contextual frameworks (e.g., differences between COVID-19 vs. viral pneumonia). The Transformer-only model characterizes long-range dependencies but has limitation capturing finer spatial detail, resulting in a combination of less accuracy and greater expense (computationally). The hybrid model takes advantage of ResNet50, mainly for low-level feature extraction and pair it will a Transformer module for high-level contextual refinement which creates a reasonable and effective solution. We demonstrated that this hybridization is advantageous to all classes equally, unlikely baselines approach in which some classes have far better results than other.

The aforementioned implications of the study-afford a significant opportunity for medical diagnostics. The model's accuracy and efficiency potentially supports radiologists in identifying

Table 3: Performance comparison of baseline models with proposed ResNet50-Transformer model

Model	Class	Accuracy (macro avg) (%)	Class-wise Accuracy	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-score (%)	Number of Epochs	Training time /Epoch
ResNet50 (CNN only)	COVID-19	88	84	88	84	86	15	10 Mins
	Normal		87	85	87	86		
	Viral Pneumonia		95	99	95	97		
	Lung Opacity		85	81	85	83		
Transformer Encoder(Self-attention)	COVID-19	69	48	77	48	59	15	12 Mins
	Normal		67	70	67	68		
	Viral Pneumonia		72	93	72	81		
	Lung Opacity		90	54	90	68		
Hybrid ResNet50 - Transformer (Proposed) (4 Class)	COVID-19	91	88	94	88	91	7	8 mins
	Normal		95	82	95	88		
	Viral Pneumonia		95	99	95	97		
	Lung Opacity		86	90	86	88		
Hybrid ResNet50 - Transformer (Proposed) (2 Class)	Class 0 (Pneumonia)	97	97	97	97	97	7	5 Mins
	Class 1 (Normal)		97	97	97	97		

diseases (like COVID-19 and pneumonia) in a more timely fashion, which may facilitate treatment for these time-sensitive illness. The model's lightweight nature also enables deployment on standard hardware, therefore providing access in communities of need. The use of train-test splits rather than cross-validation may also facilitate workflow when computational resources are scarce or when an initial quick evaluation is targeted with limited time constraints. Instead of using cross-validation to determine model performance, the train-test split evaluates model performance directly against unseen training data, therefore providing limited guidance for a primary measure of early stage model performance to facilitate comparisons or explorations. Limitations of this study remain. While the 224x224 resolution and 90:10 train-test split helped achieve results, future studies may consider iterations of cross-validation or other forms of model performance optimization, to develop measures that confirm generalizability. Because these changes can significantly alter model performance, evaluation in a clinical environment would further validate the models performance relative to other imaging protocols.

In summary, the hybrid ResNet50-Transformer model enhances chest X-ray classification by employing convolutional and attention-based modalities to achieve state-of-the-art accuracy, efficiency and flexibility. The proposed model achieves higher accuracy than the corresponding baselines of ResNet50 and/or Vision Transformer, by developing a new architecture and inventively using complementary aspects of ResNet50 and Vision Transformer. This contribution is fundamentally relevant in the development of a practical model for medical imaging. Considering the results of this pilot study done with a relatively low sample size, past research potentially shows an opportunity to increase the dataset, while future studies can also consider integrating or fusing multi-modal data (e.g. patient history) and ultimately evaluating the model in real-world clinical workflows or processes to further increase utility and robustness.

Conclusion

In this paper, a new Light weight ResNet50-Transformer Model combining CNN-based spatial feature extraction with Transformer-based global attention has resulted in 97.0% accuracy for binary classification and 91.0% accuracy for four-class lung disease classification using chest X-Ray

images. Our method provides a better baseline than existing state-of-the-art models as noted from the comparative performances in Table 3, which reveals greater classification accuracy with less training time. The architecture employs a simple ResNet50 backbone, efficient Transformer Encoder, and an image dimension reduction bottleneck utilizing 1×1 convolutions to reduce feature dimensionality while retaining spatial information. By optimizing the conventional deep learning architecture with fewer attention heads, reduced feed-forward dimensions, and minimal Transformer depth, the model learns domain invariant and domain specific features to adapt to different domains, and enhances accuracy, suggesting its potential suitability for real-world deployment in resource-limited clinical settings, pending further testing and validation.

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